

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS AND PRACTICAL IMPORTANCE OF TRADITIONAL AND INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES USED IN TEACHING ENGLISH TO PRIMARY CLASSES

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Abstract

in this article, the rapid development of the educational process requires the use of new methods and innovative technologies every day, especially the traditional and innovative methods of using modern methods and innovative technologies in the educational process in teaching foreign languages to primary school students, the comparative analysis of technologies and their role in practice are explained.

Keywords: method, innovative technology, critical and creative thinking, language sub-skills and skills, class-oriented teaching, traditional and innovative approach, passive receiver, communicative competence, reflexive skills.

In today's period of rapid development, while the position of our independent Republic in the world community is getting stronger and stronger, it is important for the youth who create the future through knowing foreign languages perfectly. Therefore, the attention paid to education in our country and the ongoing reforms are showing their results step by step. President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. M. Mirziyoyev Decision No. 312 of the Cabinet of Ministers dated May 19, 2021 No. 312 of May 19, 2021 on measures to bring the activities of to a qualitatively new level of popularization of foreign language learning in the Republic of Uzbekistan Resolution No. 610 of August 11, 2017 on measures to effectively organize the popularization of foreign language learning "On measures to further improve the quality of teaching foreign languages in educational institutions" at all stages of the continuous education system the main goal is to ensure the quality and increase the efficiency of foreign language teaching.

At present, the use of modern methods and innovative technologies in the educational process is widely promoted. One of the main reasons for this is that, until today, in traditional education, students were taught to acquire only ready-made knowledge, while the development of modern technologies allows students to search for, organize independently, think critically and creatively, analysis and even draw final conclusions. In this process, the teacher acts as a guide and creates conditions for the development, formation, acquisition of knowledge and upbringing students as individuals.

The use of modern methods and innovative technologies in teaching English to elementary school students leads to the development of students' logical and independent thinking skills, fluency in speech, the formation of quick and accurate answer skills, the awakening of enthusiasm for learning, the desire to prepare thoroughly for lessons in advance, as well as being able to understand other people's thoughts and express them verbally and in writing, the growth of speech culture, and the development of a literate person who strives for new things take a worthy place.

Today, the teacher must avoid the old traditional methods of imparting knowledge and developing language sub-skills and skills. Traditional methods of organizing training suggest the use of an information-based method. In this case, students only believe that the teacher's information is correct. For this reason, they do not want to think, discuss and independently express their opinion on the presented material. They become passive learners, lack of motivation and lack of creative thinking. In this case, the teaching process is focused on the whole group, in other words, it is class-oriented teaching. Students' tasks are to listen, understand, repeat the information and repeat it again in the next lesson.

An innovative approach to the organization of the teaching process differs from this method. At the beginning of the lesson, within the framework of the innovative approach, the teacher should explain the purpose and tasks of the lesson and the expected results at the end of the lesson. In this case, students learn actively with interest and can ask questions or express their opinions on the presented material. And the teacher continues their activity by encouraging, motivating, using new methods and technical tools. The teacher gives students the opportunity to discuss and freely express their opinions without hesitation and fear of making mistakes. The teaching process can then be adapted to the age, ability, needs and interests of the language learners. A qualified teacher can guide and support students in the language learning process and give feedback on their changes.

Comparison of traditional and innovative methods in various sources on the methodology of foreign language teaching, the following views are expressed about "Traditional Methodology":

1. The main characteristic of the traditional methodology is that "the teacher is dominant and the teacher is at the center of learning (Broughton et al., 1994).
2. "Traditional view of education where teachers are the source of knowledge and students are passive receivers" (Kuzu, 2007).
3. "Traditional education as knowledge poured from one vessel into another empty vessel.

This widespread attitude is based on the assumption that "being in the classroom with the teacher and listening attentively" is sufficient to ensure that learning takes place (Scrivener, 2005).

4. Traditional methodology – "learning under the control of the teacher" (Richards, 2008)
5. Traditional methodology does not present language as a means of communication. Rather, in this approach to teaching, "language is understood as the primary object of information learning, with an emphasis on intellectual sophistication" (White, 1988).

Unlike the traditional methodology, the modern methodology is more student-oriented, that is, students are at the center of education. According to Jim Scrivener (2005), the primary role of the teacher is to facilitate the learning process, which is to "engage" students and work at their own pace, not by giving long explanations, but by participation, conversation, includes communication and encouraging them to complete tasks. In addition, J. Broughton adds: "the skill of the teacher, who makes the language learner feel that the language is really communicative, appropriate to the context, to acquire a more complete competence in the foreign language leading practice best motivates" (Broughton, 1994).

In short, students are active in this process. In this case, the task of the teacher is not to explain, but to motivate students, and to help them learn, try, organize the learning process in an interesting way. Therefore, today the main focus is on meaning and content

The relationship between communicative competence, that is, the ability to use language for meaningful communication, is being focused on (Richards, 2008). Instead of memorizing grammar rules and specific vocabulary, modern methodology prefers to present language in context and develop skills. Taking into account the opinions of pedagogues, the following advantages and disadvantages of the traditional methods still used in the practice of foreign language teaching should be noted:

Advantages:

- ✓ the teaching process and students' activities are strictly controlled by the teacher;
- ✓ effective time allocation;
- ✓ strong discipline during the lesson;
- ✓ teaching results depend on the teacher's qualifications and influence;
- ✓ rules-instructions to reduce the elements of language and from them oral and written helps to use in speech.

Disadvantages:

- ✓ students are not active in class;
- ✓ strict control of the teaching process by the teacher is an obstacle for motivation.
- ✓ lack of direct contact between students and teacher;
- ✓ the understanding of students in the class is different and this affects the teaching results;
- ✓ insufficient conditions for decision-making;
- ✓ lack of class-oriented teaching and individual approach in the lesson.

The innovative model of teaching and learning gives teachers more advantages, but it also has disadvantages.

Advantages:

- ✓ guarantees successful results in education;
- ✓ creates favorable situations for practical use of a foreign language;
- ✓ presents different ways of explaining the educational material;
- ✓ increases motivation for learning and communication;
- ✓ creates an opportunity for students to self-assess;
- ✓ strengthens the positive attitude of students to the educational material and the educational process;
- ✓ helps students to develop critical thinking and problem solving skills;
- ✓ allows to use real (authentic) materials and create real-life situations for communication;

Disadvantages:

- ✓ takes a lot of time;
- ✓ there is a lot of noise during the lesson;
- ✓ creates a weak control or management of the teaching process by the teacher.

It can be seen that in the traditional approach, the teacher is the source of information and its deliverer. Learners are passive and they receive ready-made information, memorize it, and copy and process it. The main strategy of the teacher is to convey the information with the help of the blackboard and through speech. The teaching process is strictly controlled and the students get real knowledge.

In conclusion, the traditional method puts the responsibility for teaching and learning mainly on the teacher and believes that if the students participate in the lesson and listen to the teacher's explanations and examples, they will be able to retain the knowledge. Traditional language teaching is based on the traditional approach to foreign language learning and organization, which considers language as a collection of grammatical rules and a source of many words grouped according to rules. Therefore, in the traditional methodology, the main focus is on grammatical structures and individual elements of vocabulary.

Taking into account the above information, we found it appropriate to emphasize the following main features of innovative methods:

1. Students acquire knowledge with interest and are highly motivated, which encourages them to be active during the lesson.
2. As a result of being active, students are able to solve problems that exist during the lesson. It helps to develop creative skills in them.
3. There is an individual approach to receiving knowledge.
4. Language skills to work in pairs and groups in the organization of training

Helps to form and communicate with group members.

5. Innovative methods have a positive effect on the formation and development of self-learning and reflexive skills.
6. Interactive methods provide with using a foreign language in real life situation.
7. Students overcome the fear of making mistakes. It inspires them and motivates them to be active.

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